

MULTI-SCALE MATERIAL AND PROCESS CHARACTERIZATION FOR RESIN TRANSFER MOLDING: CASE STUDY FOR A BLENDED EPOXY/POLYBENZOXAZINE RESIN

Jonathan Lo, Mark Anders, Timotei Centea and Steven Nutt

M.C. Gill Composites Center, University of Southern California
3651 Watt Way, VHE-602, Los Angeles CA 90089-0241, United States
Email: centea@usc.edu, web page: <http://composites.usc.edu>

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ABSTRACT

The resin transfer molding of thermoset resins with complex chemical compositions can involve unusual material and process behavior. In this paper, we describe a comprehensive multi-scale approach for characterizing resin properties and in-mold phenomena, and apply it to the case of a blended epoxy/polybenzoxazine resin. The proposed methodology consists of four successive steps: (1) thermal analysis for determining temperature stability, cure kinetics, rheology and vitrification, (2) volatile analysis focused on the identity and release rate of gaseous species in processing conditions, (3) volumetric analysis for cure shrinkage and volatile-induced volumetric changes, and (4) the analysis of in-mold behavior using *in-situ* measurements and observation. The results demonstrate that, when integrated, these methods provide valuable information about the RTM of complex resins while optimizing sample scale for both measurement quantity and efficient material use, and highlight the unusual properties and behavior of the benzoxazine resin under analysis.

1 INTRODUCTION

Resin transfer molding of advanced composites involves closely-coupled resin infiltration into a complex fibrous preform, resin cure, and formation (or mitigation) of microstructural and geometric flaws. The high costs associated with designing, building and maintaining RTM tools, coupled with high-value constituent materials, call for processes, technologies and strategies that suppress defects, improve material use and energy efficiency, and minimize scrap rates [1]. As a result, successful RTM typically requires a detailed understanding of underlying physical phenomena.

Traditional resin formulations used for RTM exhibit predictable cure kinetics and low volatile release during cure. For such materials, the formation of microstructural defects is typically associated with the infiltration phase, during which voids and other flaws can form due to a combination of incomplete preform saturation and air entrapment [2]. However, the prospective use of composites in harsh environments is currently driving the development of thermoset resins that improve on traditional matrix limitations (e.g. temperature resistance, toughness, and fire-smoke-toxicity properties) at the cost of complex chemical composition and challenging in-process phenomena, including the release of volatile species and the existence of unusual defect formation mechanisms. As a result, the development of successful RTM manufacturing for such materials requires methodologies for characterizing their distinctive properties and behavior.

1.1 Traditional Material and Process Characterization

The characterization of thermosetting resins used in RTM is typically based on the thermal analysis of heat flow, mass and dimensional stability, and mechanical properties (e.g. Khoun et al. [3]). First, thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) is used to determine the onset of thermal degradation and define the maximum processing temperature. In addition, differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) is employed to determine the exothermic heat of reaction as a function of dynamic and isothermal cure cycles, as well as the evolution of the glass transition temperature. Rheometric dynamic analysis

(RDA) is used to measure the evolving viscosity (and other rheological properties) of the resin as a function of degree of cure and temperature, and to determine to gel point. Parallel-plate RDA has also been used to measure cure shrinkage after gelation through normal force control and gap monitoring [4]. Thermomechanical analysis (TMA) can be used to detect dimensional changes in processing conditions, including cure shrinkage and the evolving coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE). Finally, dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) can be employed to track the development of elastic moduli as a function of degree of cure and temperature. These experimental datasets can be used to build semi-empirical models allowing these properties to be predicted for an arbitrary cure cycle. Traditional thermal analysis is well-suited for resins exhibiting low mass loss. However, it offers limited information about non-traditional behavior such as volatile release, which can depend on both the cure reaction and external parameters such as pressure. Moreover, sample instabilities caused by volatile release (e.g. bubble formation, foaming and mass loss-induced volumetric changes) can preclude some approaches (e.g. cure shrinkage measurements using TMA or RDA).

Traditional process characterization methodologies for RTM also focus on the infiltration phase. Typical steps include determining the permeability of the fibrous preform and measuring or predicting the movement of the flow front, the extent of saturation in wetted regions, and the formation and migration of air bubbles [2]. Visual observations through transparent mold walls and embedded sensors are commonly employed (as reviewed in [2,5]). For typical RTM, process characterization does not always extend to the post-injection cure phase, since the microstructure is typically assumed stable once resin flow ceases. However, non-traditional resin behavior can engender post-injection defect formation. For example, the blended epoxy/polybenzoxazine resin used as a case study in this paper has been associated with surface porosity formation during the gelation phase [6]. For such materials, in-situ process characterization techniques must be used throughout cure, and coupled with relevant material characterization approaches. Moreover, molds used for process characterization often require large preforms to accurately capture infiltration phenomena. As a result, large quantities of materials are required for testing, and turnaround times are long.

1.2 Objectives

In this paper, we describe an expanded methodology for analysing the material properties and process phenomena associated with thermoset resins exhibiting significant mass loss during cure. Our approach couples traditional thermal analysis for cure kinetics, mass loss, rheological properties and dimensional changes with techniques for characterizing volatile release, cure and volatile-induced volumetric shrinkage, and in-mold phenomena. We employ both standard and specially designed instrumentation, and adjusts sample scale for measurement quality and efficient material use. We demonstrate the major steps of the proposed method for a complex blended resin composed of epoxy and benzoxazine constituents, currently being studied in the context of surface defect formation during RTM. In a companion paper, we focus specifically on the formation mechanisms of surface porosity and demonstrate mitigation strategies based on resin formulation and cure cycle changes [7].

2 METHODOLOGY

The proposed methodology is summarized schematically in Figure 1. It consists of four successive analysis steps associated with thermal properties, volatile release, volumetric changes and in-mold behaviour. Each step is described in detail in the following sub-sections.

2.1 Thermal Analysis

First, the thermal stability, cure kinetics/glass transition and rheological behaviour of the resin are determined using TGA (TA Instruments Q5000IR), DSC (TA Instruments Q2000) and RDA (TA Instruments AR2000ex), respectively. We carry out measurements by exposing small resin samples (10 mg to 1000 mg) to dynamic and isothermal temperature conditions, typically at ambient pressure. The resulting data describes the temperature dependence of cure and the time at which the major gelation and vitrification transitions take place. However, it provides limited insight about the identity of volatilizing species and their dependence on the other major molding condition, pressure.

Figure 1: Schematic of the proposed methodology.

2.2 Volatile Analysis

The nature and rate of volatile release are characterized using a specialized reaction cell connected to a Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectrometer (Thermo-Fisher Scientific Nicolet 4700). The reaction cell (Figure 2), adapted from a design by Advise E.E. (Greece), contains a larger resin sample than those used for thermal analysis (approx. 10 g), and can be heated and pressurized using compressed air. The head space of the sample cavity is purged with nitrogen gas at a controlled flowrate, allowing volatiles released during cure to be transported to the FTIR spectrometer. The flowrate and pressure of the purge gas is controlled using orifice plates of appropriate geometry and a gas-phase mass flow controller. The imposed temperature and pressure cycles can cure the sample in molding conditions, while the FTIR dataset clarifies the identity and timing of release of evolved species. The sample can also be weighed before and after cure to assess overall mass loss. Note that, although not shown here, the reaction cell can also be used to collect volatiles samples for other analytic chemistry tools, including nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) and gas chromatography/mass spectroscopy (GC/MS).

2.2 Volumetric Analysis

Post-gelation, thermal expansion and cure shrinkage can be measured on solid samples using traditional TMA techniques. However, volumetric changes can also occur while the resin is fluid due to volatile-induced mass loss, thermal expansion and cure shrinkage, and traditional techniques can

Figure 2: Schematics of volatile analysis instrumentation, with an inset focusing on the reaction cell.

Figure 3: Schematic of the modified pycnometry method for volumetric analysis.

also be precluded by mass loss. Thus, a modified pycnometry method is proposed to evaluate volumetric changes as a function of cure cycle and applied pressure. As shown in Figure 3, uncured resin is placed within a metallic cup, and its density (mass/volume) is measured using a pycnometer (Micromeritics AccuPyc 1330). Then, the sample is partially or fully cured in the cup within an air-pressurized fixture and oven, at known temperature and pressure. Finally, the density is re-measured. The cure shrinkage can be isolated from samples exhibiting negligible mass loss, as it is assumed to depend solely on degree of cure. For samples exhibiting mass loss, the difference between cure-induced and total volumetric change is therefore assumed to be associated with volatile release.

2.3 In-Mold Analysis

The thermal, volatile and volumetric measurements described above can effectively clarify the evolution of individual properties and the influence of specific process parameters. However, in-mold experiments are necessary to determine the combined, interacting effects of these properties and parameters on defect formation. As a result, manufacturing trials are carried out within a highly-instrumented lab-scale RTM tool configured to fabricate flat parts (Figure 4). The mold base includes resistive cartridge heaters, control and measurement thermocouples, a pressure transducer, and optional dielectric sensors (not discussed here). The top mold surface consists of a stiff tempered glass window (20 mm thick) for visual observations. Injection is unidirectional from a line inlet and carried out using a piston injector actuated by compressed air (Radius 2100). Both neat resin and composite panels can be manufactured. A digital camera (Nikon D3200) is used to record time-lapse images of the part surface during cure, while a digital microscope (Dino-Lite DinoScope) is used to capture high-resolution micrographs. The part size (127 mm by 76 mm by 3.2 mm) allows the investigation of realistic phenomena while limiting material use to approx. 100 g per part (including tubing overheads) and decreasing turnaround times compared to larger RTM molds.

Figure 4: Schematic of the instrumented RTM tool for in-mold analysis.

Table 1: Summary of case study data for a polybenzoxazine/epoxy blended resin.
“Cell” denotes the reaction cell connected to the FTIR (Figure 2).

Type	Method	Temperature	Pressure
Thermal Stab.	TGA	Dynamic	Atmospheric
Cure Kinetics	DSC	Dynamic, isothermal	Atmospheric (sealed pan)
Rheology	RDA	Dynamic	Atmospheric
Volatile Analysis	Cell-FTIR	Cure cycle	Atmospheric, Elevated
Volum. Analysis	Pycnometry	Cure cycle	Atmospheric, Elevated
Neat Resin RTM	In-Mold	Cure cycle	Atmospheric, Elevated
Composite RTM	In-Mold	Cure cycle	Elevated

2.4 Case Study

The methodology outlined above was used to characterize a polybenzoxazine/epoxy resin system intended for RTM of aerospace structures. Two non-commercial formulations developed for research were analysed: the first (F1) was minimally catalysed, while the second (F2) incorporated 2% by weight of low-temperature catalyst. The nominal injection temperature for both versions is 110°C, while the nominal manufacturer-recommended cure cycle consists of a 90 min dwell at 185°C and 450 kPa. Prior to characterization, the resin was stored frozen in sealed containers. The experimental datasets presented in this paper are summarized in Table 1.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the following sections, we present results from thermal analysis (stability, cure kinetics and rheology), volatile analysis (release kinetics and identity), volumetric analysis (shrinkage induced by cure and volatile release) and the molding of neat resin and composite panels.

3.1 Thermal Analysis

The TGA results (Figure 5A) show that both formulation exhibited non-negligible mass loss at ambient pressure and elevated temperature, with total loss percentages ranging between 10% and 12.5% for F1 (top), and 2.5% and 5% for F2 (bottom). For both materials, volatile release began above 50°C, and continued until the sample mass stabilized between 200°C and 225°C for F1 and 175°C and 200°C for F2. Prior to that point, mass loss increased non-linearly, suggesting that the mechanisms associated with inducing and terminating volatile release are distinct. Moreover, higher ramp rates led to marginally lower loss percentages, demonstrating that temperature had a direct effect. Note that the absolute amount of mass loss also depended on the ratio of surface area to volume of the sample, which is constant for a given approach (e.g. TGA) but can differ for other measurement methods. For both resins, thermal degradation began above 300°C.

The DSC data is shown in Figure 5B. Both formulations exhibited autocatalytic behavior, with a single reaction peak. Formulation F1, which was minimally catalyzed, underwent negligible cure during heat-up until abruptly and rapidly polymerizing/cross-linking between 190°C and 225°C. Conversely, the added catalyst in formulation F2 led to a comparatively gradual cure, with a measurable increase in conversion above 100°C and a decrease in the temperature and magnitude of the peak rate of reaction. Figure 5D shows summarized results from isothermal tests. The ultimate achievable degree of cure (α) increased with temperature for both formulations, though F2 was capable of fully curing at lower temperatures than F1. Conversely, the ultimate glass transition temperature (T_g) of F2 was substantially lower than that of F1 (185°C versus 230°C).

Rheological data is shown in Figure 5C for F1 (top) and F2 (bottom). For both formulations, the magnitude of the complex viscosity (η^*) decreased to approx. 0.1 Pa·s and remained constant until increasing abruptly and rapidly at gelation. Faster dynamic ramps led to gelation at higher temperatures, and F2 was gelled earlier than F1. All tests exhibited noise at low viscosities, which was caused by the limited sensitivity of parallel plate fixtures or bubble formation/volatile release.

Figure 5: Thermal analysis results from (A) TGA, (B) RDA and (C) DSC for dynamic ramps at 1°C/min, 2°C/min and 3°C/min, indicating thermal stability, rheology and cure kinetics, and (D) DSC under isothermal conditions indicating cure kinetics and glass transition temperatures.

The combined RDA and TGA results indicate that gelation likely inhibited further mass loss, and suggest that for this material, volatile release is terminated by the evolution of the resin towards a threshold mechanical state that prevents bubble formation and migration, rather than by a reduction in available volatile species.

The thermal analysis results clarify the rate and duration of the cure reaction as a function of temperature, and the relationships between polymerization/cross-linking, gelation and volatile-induced mass loss. However, they provide no information about the nature of the volatiles, the relationship between the rate of off-gassing and pressure, the volumetric changes that the resin undergoes during cure, and potential defect formation mechanisms associated with volatile release.

Figure 6: Volatile analysis data in the form of FTIR spectrographs as a function of resin, cure cycle time and absolute pressure. (A) F1, 101.3 kPa, (B) F1, 205 kPa, (C) F2, 101.3 kPa, (D) F2, 205 kPa.

3.2 Volatile Analysis

Figure 6 shows the FTIR spectroscopy results for reaction cell samples of formulations F1 and F2, cured using an injection dwell of 60 min at 110°C, a ramp of 2°C/min to 185°C, and a three-hour dwell at 185°C, under pressures of 101.3 kPa (ambient) and 205 kPa. The FTIR data consists of spectrograms measured at 35 s time intervals, and is displayed as a color map indicating unit-less absorbance, or relative signal intensity, versus wavenumber and time. Both formulations exhibited detectable off-gassing at ambient pressure, with maximum absorbance peaks occurring at the beginning of the high-temperature dwell (or the end of the heat-up ramp from 110°C to 185°C). The maximum absorbance measured for F2 was approx. 50% less than that of F1, indicating that the added catalyst inhibited volatile release, in agreement with TGA data. For both materials, absorbance levels decreased at 205 kPa, showing that higher applied pressures can effectively suppress a major portion of released volatiles for this material.

The spectrographic data relating wavenumber to absorbance can be compared against a reference library to identify probable volatiles. For F1 (Figure 6A), the primary volatile was ethyl acetate, as indicated by peaks at 2870 1/cm, 1750 1/cm, 1250 1/cm and 1055 1/cm wavenumbers, which appeared throughout cure. We also detected isohexane at the beginning of the cure cycle (3000 1/cm wavenumber). From additional tests, isohexane was associated with the mold release agent used to coat the sample cavity, and appeared only when the agent was freshly applied. Lastly, we detected phenol at ~ 150 min, as indicated by absorbance bands at 1600 1/cm, 1500 1/cm, and 750 1/cm. At 205 kPa (Figure 6B), the only detectable species was ethyl acetate, in trace amounts. For F2

Figure 7: Weight loss versus applied pressure for reaction cell/FTIR samples, with an inset showing the microstructure of a sample with significant volatility.

at ambient pressure (Figure 6C), ethyl acetate also evolved throughout cure. However, an additional volatile species, aniline, was also identified, as indicated by absorbance bands at 3442 1/cm, 3360 1/cm and 1260 1/cm. Aniline is a bulky aromatic molecule that can inhibit molecular chains from slipping past each other at high temperatures. Its volatilization during cure may explain the lower glass transition temperatures measured for formulation F2. Additionally, other species were observed to evolve during ambient temperature cure, and are believed to arise as a consequence of the catalyzed cure reaction. At 205 kPa, the F2 formulation released small quantities of ethyl acetate and aniline.

The total mass loss for samples cured within the reaction cell is shown in Figure 7. Data is only shown for formulation F2, as tests on F1 are ongoing. The results indicate that mass loss was highest at atmospheric pressure and diminished with increasing pressure until approx. 175 kPa, when it became negligible. This trend is consistent with the FTIR data (Figure 6), which indicates that molding pressures of 200 kPa are sufficient to suppress gaseous species during cure. The discrepancy in weight loss percentages between reaction cell and TGA is associated with differences in sample size and geometry (free surface area to volume).

Volatile analysis can provide valuable insights into the nature of off-gassing phenomena and the effect of temperature and pressure. FTIR spectrograms can be used to characterize the kinetics of volatile release, identify released species, and guide resin reformulation and process modifications. Meanwhile, the total mass loss data complements existing TGA by clarifying the effect of pressure and can provide simple guidelines for minimum molding conditions required to suppress volatiles for a given temperature cycle. These insights are complementary to cure kinetics, thermal stability and rheology data, and “bridge the gap” between small-scale thermal analysis and in-mold testing.

Note that similar data can in principle be obtained using a pressurized TGA-FTIR system. However, in our experience, for this material, the small samples used during TGA (circa 50 mg) led to low absorbance readings and inadequate signal-to-noise levels, even at ambient pressure. We developed the methodology presented here to accommodate larger samples and ensure signal quality across a wide pressure range, at the cost of sacrificing real-time measurement of the sample mass.

3.3 Volumetric Analysis

Figure 8A presents cure shrinkage data, extracted from samples with negligible mass loss (<1%), cured under 450 kPa at 160°C and 185°C. A linear trend-line is also included, based on previous work indicating that cure shrinkage increases linearly with degree of cure for thermoset resins [3]. The degree of cure reached at the end of each cycle is estimated from isothermal DSC data acquired during thermal analysis. For both formulations, the total cure shrinkage ($\alpha = 1$) is 1.75% to 2%. Figure 8B shows the measured volumetric changes for all test cases versus post-cure weight percent. As mentioned above, the samples cured at 450 kPa exhibited negligible mass loss, and their volumetric change was assumed to result entirely from cure shrinkage. Conversely, samples cured at ambient pressure exhibited substantially greater mass loss, and their volumetric change was decomposed into cure shrinkage (estimated from the linear trend-lines in Figure 8A) and volatile-induced volume loss (obtained by subtracting cure shrinkage from total measured volumetric decrease).

Figure 8: Volumetric analysis results: (A) volumetric cure shrinkage, (B) total volumetric decrease.

F1 samples cured at ambient pressure exhibited 5% mass loss, with 185°C cure inducing a slightly greater loss. For F2, the sample cured at 160°C and 101.3 kPa exhibited only 3.5% mass loss, whereas the mass of resin cured at 185°C decreased by 6.5%. However, the volumetric change measured for both samples was nearly equal, suggesting that experimental error (such as inhomogeneous sample structure due to micro-bubble entrapment) may affect volume measurements during low-pressure cure. Nevertheless, the modified pycnometry method presented here enables the measurement of volumetric changes as a function of pressure, the direct measurement of cure shrinkage at high pressures, and the approximate distinction of cure and volatile-induced volumetric changes for other molding conditions.

3.4 In-Mold Analysis

The data obtained from thermal, volatile and volumetric analysis provides valuable insights into material behavior under process-relevant temperature and pressure cycles. However, in-mold analysis is required to clarify key defect formation mechanism and capture tooling-dependent phenomena. Molding tests were carried out on neat resin and composite panels, and are described below.

Neat resin panels were fabricated using the lab-scale mold and traditional RTM injection protocols. Figure 8 summarizes the manufacturing outcomes by indicating whether combinations of cure temperature and molding pressure resulted in porous or void-free parts. Results are presented solely for formulation F1, as tests on F2 are ongoing and, based on previous results, both formulations are similarly influenced by pressure. Neat resin panels exhibited a threshold pressure band between 150 kPa and 200 kPa, in agreement with volatile analysis. Resin cured below 150 kPa exhibited significant void nucleation and growth, while resin processed at 200 kPa and above contained no porosity. The critical pressure increased slightly with temperature. For example, a neat resin panel cured at 160 kPa and 170°C presented no voids, while panels cured under the same pressure at 185°C and 200°C contained porosity. The transparent plate of the lab-scale RTM mold enabled direct observation of formation mechanisms. When voids developed, they nucleated on the hotter/metallic surface of the mold cavity, grew rapidly, and sometimes migrated upwards. Void nucleation, growth and movement ceased at resin gelation. Samples cured at higher temperature exhibited much faster void growth. Note, again, that the porosity shown in Figure 8 was not caused by entrapped air: resin was de-gassed under vacuum (< 10 kPa) at above-ambient temperature (110°C) for one hour, and the glass mold surface confirmed that no air bubbles were present within the mold cavity at the end of injection.

Figure 9: Bulk porosity map for neat resin panels (F1) versus cure temperature and pressure, with inset photographs showing neat resin panels with and without bulk porosity.

Composite panels were fabricated using the lab-scale mold, traditional RTM injection protocols, and carbon fiber fabric preforms (Sigmatex 3K five harness satin weave, 365 g/m², with binder). Figure 9 shows representative data for part temperature, supply pressure and resin pressure, measured *in situ* during cure for F1 and F2 formulations injected at 110°C and cured at 185°C, under approx. 450 kPa. Following mold heat-up and resin injection (which occurred rapidly and without air entrapment), as the mold temperature was raised towards the cure dwell, the supply and cavity pressures were approximately equal. However, early during the dwell, the resin pressure exhibited a precipitous drop, descending towards negative (or tensile stress) values. This sudden decrease, hypothesized to occur due to cure shrinkage, led to separation between the part and tool surface and caused significant surface porosity on the colder, glass-side surface of the part manufactured from F1, and trace surface porosity for F2. Interestingly, surface voids were observed to nucleate and growth as the cavity pressure descended below the threshold pressure region required to suppress volatile release (150 kPa to 200 kPa, shown in color in Figure 9). The mechanisms underlying the formation of this specific defect type, as well as material and process parameter-based mitigation strategies, are discussed in a companion paper [7].

Figure 10: Temperature and pressure measurements from RTM of composite panels, with digital micrographs showing the formation of surface porosity on the glass-side surface of the curing part.

In-mold characterization offers critical insights into the interplay of material behavior and process parameters. The processing of neat resin panels allows investigation of trends from thermal and volatile analysis in actual processing conditions (i.e. injection and closed cavity molding), and enables visual observation of bulk porosity formation as a function of real-time temperature and pressure. The composite manufacturing tests replicate industrial manufacturing protocols in a controlled and instrumented molding tool, whose embedded sensors and transparent mold surface enable the monitoring of process conditions during cure, the visualization of the flow front during injection, and the formation of surface defects during all stages of processing. In both cases, the size of the manufactured panels is sufficiently large to allow industrially relevant phenomena to occur, but small enough to limit material use and enable rapid mold turnaround times.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The demand for composite materials with improved mechanical, thermal and chemical properties has led to the development of resin matrices with complex chemical compositions. Such materials can exhibit complicated in-process behavior during RTM, including non-negligible volatile release and unusual defect formation mechanisms, and must be thoroughly characterized.

In this paper, we described a methodology for comprehensive material and process characterization of resins with volatilizing behavior, and demonstrated the methodology for an epoxy/polybenzoxazine system. Thermal analysis was first used to assess thermal stability, cure kinetics and rheology. These tests clarified the temperature-dependence of the polymerization/cross-linking reaction and the timing of major transitions. Volatile release was analyzed by means of a custom-built reaction cell connected to an FTIR spectrometer. FTIR analysis of gas-phase species and sample mass measurements were used to determine the nature and release kinetics of the volatiles as a function of cure cycle and pressure. The results indicated that, for the material under study, a critical threshold pressure of 150 kPa to 200 kPa is necessary and sufficient to suppress volatile-induced mass loss. Volumetric changes during processing were analysed using a modified pycnometry technique. Resin samples were cured within pycnometer cups at several temperatures and pressures. Samples with negligible weight loss were used to determine cure shrinkage as a function of temperature (and degree of cure), while volumetric changes for samples with measurable mass loss were decomposed into cure and mass-loss-induced components. Finally, we used in-mold manufacturing trials to correlate previous results with actual defect formation mechanisms. Neat resin and composite panels were fabricated using an instrumented RTM tool with a transparent mold wall. The neat resin tests were used to observe bulk porosity formation as a function of temperature and pressure, while the composite trials highlighted the formation of surface porosity due to shrinkage-induced pressure variations.

The comprehensive methodology described here complements and enhances existing protocols for characterizing RTM, which have typically been developed for non-volatilizing matrices and consist mainly of thermal analysis and infiltration monitoring:

- (1) The volatile and volumetric analysis protocols clarify the effect of pressure, and therefore offer critical information that is typically unavailable.
- (2) The volumetric analysis technique also avoids issues associated with using microstructurally unstable samples of volatilizing resins to determine cure shrinkage using other methods (e.g. TMA or normal force control RDA).
- (3) In-mold analysis using instrumented tooling with a transparent mold face allows phenomena identified using thermal, volatile and volumetric analysis to be investigated within an actual molding environment, and enables the identification and visual observation of defect formation mechanisms at all stages of processing.
- (4) The integrated nature of the methodology promotes progressive scale-up, and enables insights gained using one approach to be verified and improved using others. For example, within the case study presented in this paper, volatile release was characterized using TGA, the reaction cell/FTIR system and in-mold neat resin panels. Off-gassing was consistently associated with a threshold pressure level of 150 kPa to 200 kPa, and was shown to cause both bulk and surface porosity (depending on the nominal applied pressure).

- (5) Multiple sample scales are used to ensure measurement quality while lowering material use. The samples required for thermal analysis are relatively small (10 mg to 50 mg). Material quantities used for volatile and volumetric analysis are typically larger (1 g to 10 g) to allow adequate detectability, but remain reasonable. The lab-scale RTM tool used for in-mold analysis is compact, enabling low material use and turnaround times, but is sufficiently large to ensure relevant phenomena are captured.

Process characterization methodologies are an essential component of material and process development. These techniques presented here, along with others, can clarify fundamental material behaviour and process phenomena, and identify improvements that prevent defect formation, improve production rates and yields, and reduce waste. These desirable outcomes can support and foster the increased use of composites, and enable insertion of new materials and processes into service.

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